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Abstract

This deliverable report outlines the final version of the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service in the context of Work Package 4 (WP4) of the SciLake project, focusing on the development and extension of the capabilities of the service since its initial version. This service aims to contribute in tackling aspects related to the reproducibility crisis in scientific research by leveraging the rich data within the Scientific Lake. By enhancing Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) with critical information on research outputs, the service aids researchers in identifying reproducible studies and understanding the extent to which scientific findings have been replicated.

DRAFT

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Abbreviation List

DOI	Digital Object Identifier
ROR	Research Organization Registry
NER	Named-entity Recognition
NEN	Named-entity Normalisation
GDD	Graph Generating Dependency
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
KG	Knowledge Graph
LLM	Large Language Model
LoRA	Low Rank Adaptation
NMT	Neural Machine Translation
RA	Research Artefact
RAA	Research Artefact Analysis
SKG	Scientific Knowledge Graph
TSV (file)	Tab Separated Values (file)
UI	User Interface

1. Executive Summary

In this report, we describe the final version of the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service, developed as part of the SciLake project. This service leverages the contents of SciLake's SKGs and the various technologies provided by SciLake's Scientific Lake architecture, and its main aim is to address the reproducibility crisis in scientific research by assessing and enhancing the reproducibility and replicability of research outputs, through the automated extraction of additional information that complements and reinforces their documentation.

Transparency of methods ensures that procedures, materials, and analytical techniques used in research are clearly described, allowing other researchers to reanalyze data, verify results,

and potentially uncover new insights or corrections. This is hindered by the lack of a standardised manner in which these resources are described or shared, as well as how they are cited in other works, often remaining “hidden” in footnotes or in-text mentions—as opposed to appearing as structured references. Furthermore, the quality of scholarly research and the reliability of research findings cannot be accurately assessed based on citation numbers alone, since they do not account for the context or content of these citations. High citation counts can result from factors unrelated to research quality, such as the popularity of a topic, self-citations, or citations in negative contexts. This makes it difficult for others to assess and replicate studies accurately, especially when navigating vast amounts of research outputs.

In light of the above, the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service provides functionalities to help researchers assess and identify reliable studies in a standardised manner when sifting through large volumes of works. It does so by employing state-of-the-art natural-language processing techniques to (a) automatically parse the structure of scientific documents, standardising their constituent parts and translating their content if needed; (b) extract and categorise mentions to research resources introduced and/or (re)used by a given work, along with mentions to domain-specific technologies and/or concepts of interest; (c) uncover missing links between different outputs in the SKGs, and between outputs and their contributors; and (d) analyse the context in which citations between these outputs occur, providing insights on the reception of a given work’s findings among the scientific community.

The service architecture is designed for it to be adaptable to different scientific domains. Within the project, and in order to test them in real-life scenarios, service functionalities are tailored to the specific domains of the project pilots: Cancer research, Neuroscience, Energy, Transport-Maritime, and Transport-CCAM. The components of the service are loosely coupled to allow for flexibility of integration. Within the project’s proofs of concept, the components’ outputs are aggregated into reproducibility-related badges that serve as convenient visual indicators of the degree of completeness and availability of the metadata and resources of a collection of scientific works, in addition to the level of trustworthiness of their findings. This enables researchers to streamline the discovery of robust and repeatable research workflows and outputs, helping improve transparency and rigour in scientific publishing.

2. Introduction

Current scientific research moves at a vigorous pace, producing vast amounts of rich, valuable knowledge from a plethora of sources; however, this rapid proliferation of information has some potential drawbacks. The number of manuscripts submitted for peer review is growing more and more every year, and the resulting increased workload for editors and reviewers, who are tasked with the in-depth scrutiny of the soundness and clarity of the methods and reported findings, has the potential to jeopardise the overall rigour of the process.

The traditional peer review system itself is not without its flaws, being plagued by issues of bias amplification and lack of transparency, to name a few, and a number of alternatives have been proposed, including continuous post-publication review. This, and the proliferation of preprint repositories, results in researchers facing not only an enormous scale of potentially valuable information, but also, in many cases, without the “seal of approval” of formal peer review. Furthermore, the production of scientific knowledge can take many forms, and publications are only one item in an ever-expanding list of research outputs that researchers can build upon.

The sheer scale of information makes it difficult for researchers to navigate the scientific landscape and identify high-quality, credible works. This is especially relevant in the context of the “reproducibility crisis” affecting research [1], with a large number of studies that are not amenable to verification due to lack of transparency or issues of availability—details buried behind paywalls, or unreleased data—while a few others report conclusions of dubious validity. One of the aspects contributing to the former is the lack of a standardised manner in which to cite research outputs other than publications—e.g., datasets, software—so that the connections between these heterogeneous sources are exposed in vast collections of data. Recent attempts at addressing this issue include repositories that endow research outputs other than publications with a persistent identifier, thus making them citable in a traditional fashion—e.g., Zenodo. However, despite these efforts, most of these references remain hidden from standard research metadata—they only appear in, e.g., footnotes or direct in-text mentions. This makes identifying the connection between scientific findings and a given resource a very difficult task, and hinders a thorough understanding of resource use, reuse, and impact.

Here, we present the final version of the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service of the SciLake project. This service aims to address the technical challenges in the assessment of

research reproducibility. It leverages the contents of the Scientific Lake and advanced text mining to enrich the SKGs with valuable information in the form of new connections among research outputs, and between research outputs and relevant domain-specific concepts and technologies, in addition to providing insights into the validity of research findings via citation context analysis. This facilitates knowledge discovery by highlighting research outputs that are more likely to be reproducible, and showing the extent to which their findings have been replicated. This information is key for researchers to get a quick overview of the scientific works they may use as a base for their own studies.

While the project adopts four scientific domains as use cases, the technologies presented below have been developed with adaptability in mind and, with minimal effort, can be adjusted to provide similar functionalities across different domains of scholarly content, enhancing the overall capability of the scientific lake to support the needs of diverse research communities. In the following sections, we provide a comprehensive overview of the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service: sections 3 and 4 detail the design and implementation (respectively) of the major components of the service implemented by the SciLake partners. These include research object recognition, named-entity recognition and normalisation, link recommendation, article segmentation and translation, citation-context assisted replication assessment. The integration of these components into reproducibility-related badges is discussed in Section 5. Finally, Section 6 summarises the work performed in the development and implementation of the service.

3. Design and functionalities

The aim of this service is to address the reproducibility crisis in scientific research by assessing and enhancing the reproducibility and replicability of research outputs. The components of the service—designed as a collection of loosely-coupled enrichment workflows—provide researchers with tools to better understand and pursue reproducibility in scientific findings by enhancing both the documentation of the works available in the SKGs at the individual level, and the connections among works and between works and other relevant entities, in order to obtain a more nuanced picture of the resources used by a given study, or the technologies pertinent to it, in addition to the reception of its findings within the scientific community. The service allows for these enrichments to be implemented in a standardised language- and section-aware fashion, thereby providing an additional level of granularity and the possibility of integrating English and non-English sources.

As described in more detail in D4.1 (“Initial version of the smart reproducibility assistance service”)¹, the individual components that make up the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service support the following functionalities:

- Research object recognition in textual data. The automated extraction of mentions of datasets and software from scientific texts aims to give researchers a detailed overview of the resources utilised in scientific studies, enhancing transparency of methods and tools and promoting the replication of methodological workflows and the validation of scientific findings.
- Recognition of domain-specific research objects. The identification of technologies and domain-specific terms within research outputs, and their standardisation using established or ad-hoc taxonomies, enables end-users to get a swift overview of relevant works and the groupings between them when navigating vast amounts of data.
- Geolocalisation. Extracting and integrating the geographic information within research outputs can provide novel insights and a more nuanced picture of the relationship and interplay between the location of research institutions and the locations that are the research focus.
- Research object link recommendation. The identification and filling of gaps between research objects and research stakeholders and contributors plays a crucial role in enabling scientific reproducibility by enhancing the documentation and traceability of research outputs.
- Article segmentation for multilingual articles. This component analyses the structure of scientific documents by identifying their constituent parts and normalising them so that sections that play an equivalent role are treated equivalently despite potential discrepancies in naming conventions, thereby expediting researchers’ understanding of document structure and organisation.
- Citation-context assisted replication assessment. The analysis of the precise context in which research is cited and/or reused provides researchers with a nuanced understanding of the extent to which scientific methodologies can be reproduced and scientific findings verified, enhancing the transparency and reliability of research.

In conjunction, the outputs of these tools can be visually summarised as reproducibility and replicability badges within the UI of the Smart Impact-driven Discovery Service—see D3.2 (“Final version of the smart impact-driven discovery service”)²—serving as straightforward

¹ doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13239445

² doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18328003

indicators that enable users to easily identify research outputs with comprehensive methodological details and verified findings or, conversely, to recognise those with potential limitations or flaws, consequently aiding the promotion of transparency and trustworthiness in scientific research.

4. Implementation

In this section, we detail the individual components of the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service and their integration into the Scientific Lake. Building upon the work performed during the first half of the project, and described in D4.1, we have refined and consolidated methodologies, and extended the scope and capabilities of the components, in addition to implementing new functionalities geared towards providing a tailored experience to the research communities participating as pilots in the project.

4.1. Research object recognition in textual data

In this section, we elaborate on the components designed to automatically recognise and extract mentions of research objects in scientific publication manuscripts or other scientific texts. Each of the components focuses on different types of research objects. In the next sections, first, we provide background on the problem of research object recognition in textual data and explain how it can help in enhancing research reproducibility. Then, we provide the technical details related to each of the aforementioned components.

4.1.1. Background

Components that are able to extract mentions of datasets, software, technologies and other domain-specific entities from scientific publication manuscripts or other scientific textual data can contribute in enhancing the reproducibility of research. By automatically identifying and cataloguing these entities in Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), these components provide a comprehensive map of the resources used in research works. Researchers can then quickly access detailed information about the datasets and software employed, which is essential for replicating experiments and validating results. They can also quickly identify how easy it is for other researchers to reproduce their own work. This transparency ensures that all the tools and data necessary for reproduction are clearly documented, reducing the ambiguity that often hampers reproducibility efforts. A series of reproducibility-related badges and/or

indicators can be calculated using this information, offering convenience to researchers and other stakeholders.

Moreover, the respective enrichments to the SKGs can significantly streamline the research process. For instance, by identifying and linking mentions of genes and diseases across different studies, researchers can gain insights into how they are related, and identify novel associations and potential avenues for further investigation. The same applies to datasets and software, where connections between studies using similar resources can be made. This interconnected approach not only aids in the verification of individual studies but also facilitates meta-analyses and the synthesis of broader trends within a field. Ultimately, this enhances the overall reliability and robustness of scientific research, fostering a more transparent and reproducible scientific ecosystem.

4.1.2. SciNoBo RAA tool: Recognition of Datasets & Software

The **SciNoBo Research Artefact Analysis (RAA) tool**³ performs RAA on scientific texts to identify mentions of research artefacts (RAs) such as datasets and software. It extracts these mentions along with their associated metadata and then deduplicates them to determine the unique RAs that were referenced, reused, or created in the text (see Figures 4.1.2.1 [1] and 4.1.2.2 [2]). The final version of the tool leverages language models (SciBERT or ModernBERT) and relies on a predefined list of discipline-specific keywords, key phrases, and gazetteers⁴ to detect candidate mentions of RAs. Extracted artefacts are integrated into the SciLake Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) where they support reproducibility assessment and resource discovery.

Figure 1: An overview of how the SciNoBo RAA tool works.

³ github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-rra

⁴ Lists of known entities from an external source.

Snippet	In their study, the authors utilized the PyTorch <code><m>library</m></code> (version 1.9.0) for deep learning experiments. PyTorch is released under the BSD-3-Clause license. For more information, visit https://pytorch.org/ .
Type	Software
Valid	Yes
Name	PyTorch
Version	1.9.0
License	BSD-3-Clause
URL	https://pytorch.org/
Provenance	No
Usage	Yes

Figure 2: An example of an RA mention containing all metadata.

SYSTEM OVERVIEW

As detailed in D4.1, the tool relied on a Question Answering (QA) formulation based on fine-tuned Large Language Models (LLMs) and an optional Coreference Resolution Longformer model (SciCo)⁵ [2], combined with discipline-specific keyword lists, key phrases, and gazetteers, to detect candidate RA mentions. Although this approach demonstrated strong results [15], the use of LLMs (we also experimented with a Llama3.1 variant) proved to be time-consuming for the large scale processing that the project requires. As a result, we reformulated research artefact recognition as a **Named Entity Recognition (NER) and classification task**, leveraging transformer-based models pretrained on scientific text. In particular, SciBERT was adopted as the primary backbone model, enabling token-level detection of dataset and software mentions and improving robustness across disciplines and time inference speeds.

1. Research Artefact Validation:

This stage filters sentences containing research artefacts, by using the NER-based model to mark relevant paragraphs containing RAs for further evaluation, and then validating each candidate sentence, classifying the RA mentions as valid or generic references. The latter uses a series of keywords and keyphrases from a human-curated list as triggers for datasets and software mentions, in addition to gazetteers from the PapersWithCode (PwC) dataset⁶ that help directly identify mentions by name.

⁵ SciCo Longformer model is designed for handling long scientific documents and it is used to perform hierarchical cross-document coreference resolution.

⁶ github.com/paperswithcode/paperswithcode-data

Each candidate RA mention is assigned a validity score against a set threshold, and those surpassing the threshold are considered valid, while the rest are considered generic references. Figure 4.1.2.3 [3] summarises the Research Artefact Validation pipeline.

Figure 3: Research Artefact Validation pipeline.

2. Research Artefact Metadata Extraction & Classification:

This stage focuses on the research artefact metadata and on its ownership and usage status. The former step focuses on extracting the name, version, licence, and URL from the RA mention, while the latter classifies whether the RA has been created by the authors or (re)used in their work. Figure 4.1.2.4 [4] illustrates the Research Artefact Metadata extraction and classification pipeline.

Figure 4: Research Artefact Metadata extraction & classification pipeline.

3. Research Artefact Deduplication & Re-evaluation:

The final stage consolidates RA mentions, using their context and metadata to deduplicate and reevaluate them, clustering them into unique artefacts. The process leverages the SciCo Longformer model to provide similarity scores for hierarchical cross-document coreference resolution.

At this stage, the metadata and the classification into "owned" and "reused" is also refined based on the consolidated context and aggregated metadata of each deduplicated RA. Figure 4.1.2.5 [5] provides an overview of the Research Artefact deduplication and re-evaluation pipeline.

Figure 5: Research Artefact deduplication & re-evaluation pipeline.

LLM-as-a-Judge evaluation, gold metadata creation

To systematically assess the quality and contextual correctness of the extracted metadata (we sampled publications from the Scilake Pilots and inferred them with the NER-based method) and to minimise noise before manual annotation, an LLM-as-a-Judge evaluation framework was introduced for this second version of the deliverable. In this setup, independent LLM judges verify whether the metadata associated with a specific research artefact mention is accurate and justified based solely on the textual mention. Both proprietary and open-source judge models were explored; however, the final judging pipeline relied on two independent judges, Claude 3.5 Haiku and GPT-4o-mini, evaluated under the same structured schema.

To ensure high precision, each candidate mention from the original corpus result was first evaluated by both judges, who were prompted to infer and validate the artefact metadata using a strict JSON output structure. A mention was allowed to progress to manual verification

only if: (i) both LLMs agreed on the inferred metadata, and (ii) their outputs matched exactly under the required JSON structure. This agreement filter removed the majority of ambiguous or noisy mentions early, reducing manual effort and increasing the consistency of the curated set.

After this automated pass, manual verification was performed across all remaining items to correct residual judge errors. This included fixing name mismatches, ensuring usage and ownership align with the mention text, removing hallucinated URLs or versions, verifying that only the correct artefact is tagged, and ensuring every metadata field remains consistent with the original evidence. The resulting dataset forms a gold dataset, manually validated set of research artefact mentions covering the Fields of Science of interest to the project.

Data Augmentation Approach

To better support domain adaptation and specifically better cover the SciLake pilot domains (neuroscience, cancer research, energy, and transport), the aforementioned gold dataset was expanded using an LLM-driven augmentation strategy. The goal of augmentation was not merely to increase dataset size, but to also add types of cases where our models typically fail. As a consequence, augmentation was deliberately biased towards difficult, yet valid cases: mentions that are valid and metadata-consistent, but syntactically, semantically, or structurally challenging.

Key approaches included:

- Artefact mentions that are correct and consistent with the metadata, but difficult to interpret. These include comparative sentences (e.g. “unlike SciPy, <m>Tool</m> provides...”), mentions containing multiple entities where only one is the actual artefact, cases with several URLs or licences where only one applies to the tagged artefact, and complex sentence structures such as parentheticals, long noun phrases, fronted clauses (e.g. “Using <m>Tool</m>, we...”), or multi-clause sentences with coreference.
- Instances with artefacts that include explicit Version, License, or URL information. This forces the models to learn where such metadata typically appears in text, which entity it refers to, and when it should not be assigned to the tagged artefact, reducing incorrect metadata propagation from nearby tools or datasets.
- We included variation in sentence length, syntactic structure, and discourse style (e.g. active vs. passive voice, fronted constructions, appositive phrases).
- We created examples with verbs typical of software (e.g. run, simulate, analyze) and phrasing typical of datasets (e.g. drawn from, sourced from, evaluated on). At the same time, usage labels were controlled: when Usage was set to “Yes”, each sentence explicitly stated that the authors used the artefact in the study; when Usage was set to

“No”, sentences were restricted to neutral or third-person descriptions, without implying author usage.

Finally, generation was performed using Claude 3.5 Haiku that produced additional artefact mentions for each valid instance of the gold dataset, together with a set of challenging cases used for evaluation. These cases included incorrect URL or version assignments, wrong artefact names inside <m> tags, mis-tagged generic terms (e.g. tagging “data” as an artefact), and type mismatches such as treating datasets as software. All generated sentences were required to strictly follow the provided metadata schema, contain exactly one <m>...</m> tag, and avoid inventing any missing information. Outputs were carefully validated, deduplicated, and separated into positive and challenging sets for training and evaluation⁷. Currently there is also a ModernBERT variant being trained. Results can be provided in the evaluation deliverable for this component. Results from the SciBERT variant are incorporated into the Scientific Knowledge Graphs and are viewed and evaluated from the pilots in their respective BiP!Spaces.

USEFUL RESOURCES

The next table summarises the most important resources (publications, code repositories, etc) related to the SciNoBo RAA tool.

Paper(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Empowering Knowledge Discovery from Scientific Literature: A novel approach to Research artefact Analysis• Streamlining Knowledge Discovery in Scientific Literature: A Comprehensive End-to-End System for Research Artefact Analysis (submitted to EMNLP 2024)
Code repo(s)	github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-raa
Docker hub	hub.docker.com/repository/docker/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-raa/general
HF Space (Demo)	huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-research-artefact-analysis

Table 1: Links to code repositories and documentation of the field extraction component.

⁷ The dataset is available in the following github repo: <https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-raa>

4.1.3. Recognition of domain-specific research objects

With the objective of facilitating the exploration of the content of the Scientific Lake for the end-users of the project pilots, we have worked on the identification of mentions to domain-specific concepts and entities of interest for the respective research communities within the text of the research outputs in the SKGs. Coupled to a mapping of these mentions to canonical entries in relevant domain-specific taxonomies, we are able to enrich the corresponding graphs by suggesting potential connections between research outputs and relevant concepts in a structured fashion, which not only serve to provide an enhanced knowledge discovery experience, but can also be exploited down the line to connect to other annotated sources.

During the first half of the project, we focused on the identification of entities relevant to the biomedical domain. As detailed in D4.1, we trained a set of AIONER [3] models to identify a collection of standard biomedical entities: *gene*, *disease*, *chemical*, *species*, *cell line*, *variant*. We also extended this list to include a selection of anatomical entities from the AnatEM corpus⁸: *cell*, *cell component*, *tissue*, *multi-tissue structure*, *organ*; in addition to *cancer*, included in the latest version of the dataset. These models constitute a strong baseline that can be used to enrich SKGs from a wide variety of domains, and have been specifically applied to the case of the Cancer pilot.

A natural next step was then to focus on the Neuroscience pilot, due to its biomedical nature. However, while we have used the AIONER models as a starting point for the enrichment of the Neuroscience outputs, the initial set of biomedical entities only partially aligns with the pilot's needs; specifically, the need to connect publications with other curated research outputs from EBRAINS⁹ through relevant concepts, manually annotated in the case of the latter. Therefore, in collaboration with the pilot representatives, we selected and prioritised a set of entities from the list of openMINDS controlled terms¹⁰, such as *technique* or *preparationType*.

For the remaining pilots, the approach was similar. Due to their specific needs and idiosyncrasies, the effort was focused towards creating a solution that could accommodate them all individually, in order to provide a tailored experience while being as domain-agnostic as possible. This ensures the enrichment pipeline—detailed below—can be adapted to new use cases with minimal effort. In particular, both the Energy and Maritime Transport pilots

⁸ nactem.ac.uk/anatomytagger/#AnatEM

⁹ ebrains.eu/

¹⁰ openminds.docs.om-i.org/en/latest/schema_specifications/controlledTerms.html

required identifying relevant concepts—*energyType* and *vesselType*, respectively—in publication texts and connecting them to pertinent regulatory or legal documents, either manually annotated or enriched by the same tool. A special interest in the geolocalisation of research outputs in the case of the Energy pilot has been tackled with a different approach, as shown below.

Finally, for the case of CCAM, in addition to a set of more straightforward entities, such as *sensor type*, there was an interest in capturing the SAE levels of automation¹¹ mentioned or referred to in research outputs. We have done this via an entity that includes, within its scope, not only the direct mention of the levels themselves (e.g., “level 2”) but also any relevant automation technology (e.g., “adaptive cruise control”); this, in conjunction with a mapping from technology-related terms to the relevant automation levels, provides a richer picture than simply extracting explicit level mentions.

By way of summary, the full list of entities for each pilot can be found in the following Table

Pilot	Entity	Examples	Relevant taxonomy
Cancer	gene	myoglobin; β -lactoglobulin; kras	NCBI Gene ¹²
	disease	sarcoma; pancreatic adenocarcinoma; prostate cancer	Disease Ontology ¹³
	chemical	carbon monoxide; histidine; fatty acids	DrugBank ¹⁴
	species	mice; human; bovine	NCBI Taxonomy ¹⁵
	cell line	k422; 293t; a375	BRENDA Tissue Ontology ¹⁶
Neuroscience	technique	DNA sequencing; sodium MRI; voltage clamp	openMINDS
	preparation type	in vitro; in vivo	openMINDS

¹¹

sae.org/standards/j3016_202104-taxonomy-definitions-terms-related-driving-automation-systems-road-motor-vehicles

¹² ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gene/

¹³ disease-ontology.org/

¹⁴ go.drugbank.com/

¹⁵ ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy/

¹⁶ ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/bto

	UBERON parcellation	spinal cord; pineal tract; medial orbital frontal cortex	UBERON ¹⁷ , restricted to Central Nervous System
	species	mice; human; bovine	openMINDS
	biological sex	male; female	openMINDS
Energy	energy type	biogas; photovoltaic; peat	IRENA ¹⁸
	energy storage	pumped hydro storage; thermal storage; ultracapacitors	IRENA
Transport - Maritime	vessel type	bulk carrier; ferry; yacht	Ad-hoc based on AIS ship types ¹⁹
Transport - CCAM	vehicle type	car; truck; shuttle	Ad-hoc based on SINFONICA ²⁰ and FAME ²¹
	VRU type	pedestrian; scooter; bicycle	Ad-hoc based on SINFONICA and FAME
	communication type	5G; cellular communication; DSRC	Ad-hoc based on SINFONICA and FAME
	entity connection type	vehicle-to-pedestrian; I2X; V2V	Ad-hoc based on SINFONICA and FAME
	sensor type	camera; LIDAR; odometer	Ad-hoc based on SINFONICA and FAME
	scenario type	platooning; traffic scenario; test scenario	Ad-hoc based on SINFONICA and FAME
	level of automation (via automation technologies)	electronic stability control; lane centering; park assist	Ad-hoc based on SINFONICA and FAME

Table 2: Entity types for the domain-specific concept extraction.

¹⁷ ebi.ac.uk/ols4/ontologies/uberon

¹⁸ irena.org/Publications/2024/Mar/Energy-taxonomy-Classifications-for-the-energy-transition

¹⁹ api.vtexplorer.com/docs/ref-aistypes.html

²⁰ sinfonica.eu/building-a-comprehensive-ccam-vocabulary-for-all/

²¹ taxonomy.connectedautomateddriving.eu/

SAMPLE GENERATION FOR NAMED-ENTITY RECOGNITION

As the initial step, a small sample of documents for each of the pilots of the project was extracted from a collection of publications belonging to their relevant scientific domains, which we parsed and segmented by section with GROBID²². For each publication, we extracted the title, abstract, and up to 2 randomly chosen sections from its body—yielding a total of 150–200 samples—and generated pseudolabels using an LLM. In particular, we created a project in Claude²³ with overall extraction instructions and select domain- and entity-specific considerations. Each prompt then consisted of a file containing a batch of documents to be annotated, and the resulting labels include the entity text, entity type, and linked entity, for cases for which we had previously defined a taxonomy to be used for entity linking. From these pseudolabels we also generated the spans corresponding to the extracted entities using regular expressions as a post-processing step, as we were unable to obtain consistent results for the positions of the entities directly from the LLM.

We show an example of project instructions below, with specific considerations for the case of the Energy pilot:

```
Extract and categorise these [DOMAIN_NAME] entities from the given texts using [REFERENCE_TAXONOMY], focusing on precise entity identification.
```

```
Entity types:
```

1. ...
2. ...

```
The taxonomy is provided as [CSV/PDF] along with these instructions.
```

```
Output Format:
```

```
For each document, produce a json output of the form
```

```
{
  "id": "document_identifier",
  "entities": [
    {
      "entity": the EXACT entity text
```

²² A dataset containing 1,000 full-text papers from each domain: Neuroscience, Cancer, Transport, and Energy, along with an additional 1,000 random papers from general scientific domains, and curated with licenses that allow for legal usage, specifically CC-BY and Public Domain, is available at huggingface.co/datasets/SIRIS-Lab/scilake-fulltext-corpus.

²³ claude.ai

```
"label": the entity type,  
"linked entity": name of the entity in the provided taxonomy  
"linked id": taxonomy entity ID  
}  
]  
}
```

Entity Linking Rules

Match to the closest entry in the taxonomy provided, paying attention to the definition of each entry. Use your judgement but DO NOT GUESS trying to be more specific than the text implies. If you believe you have identified a correct entity type but find no match on the table, set the linked entity to "Other"

Entity Extraction Guidelines

When identifying and categorizing entities according to the taxonomy, follow these strict guidelines:

The 'entity' field must contain the exact text as it appears in the document (maintaining capitalisation). When an acronym is introduced with its full form (e.g., 'electroencephalogram (EEG)'), extract the complete text including both the full form and the acronym. When only the acronym is used subsequently (e.g., just 'EEG'), extract only the acronym. Never expand acronyms that aren't explicitly expanded in the text, and never modify the entity text in any way from how it originally appears.

Precision and Evidence

Only map entities to taxonomy categories when there is explicit textual evidence supporting that specific categorisation. Do not make assumptions about entities based on common associations if not stated in the text. Maintain a high standard of evidence---if in doubt, do not extract the entity.

Do not ignore documents without extracted entities. Provide outputs for all documents even if empty.

Additional Instructions for Entity Extraction

energyType: Focus on tangible fuel sources or primary energy conversion methods. Do not include abstract energy forms like 'kinetic energy', 'potential energy', or 'electrical energy', nor generic terms such as simply 'energy' or 'electricity'. Less generic terms, like 'renewable energy', should be included.

SAMPLE VALIDATION AND MODEL TRAINING

The LLM-generated labels and the extracted spans, while not being perfect, provide a starting point for data annotation that can be further refined down the line. We set up a validation

interface using the Argilla annotation tool²⁴, and requested an evaluation of the initial samples by the domain experts for our five different use cases. For each text, they were presented with its extracted entities, if any, highlighted according to their entity types, along with their potential links to the specified taxonomy. They had the option to: create new spans and/or fix existing ones; select whether the entities and their types were correctly extracted; and select whether the suggested links made sense—see image below. This UI-based approach allowed the experts to efficiently engage with the data and helped streamline the development process.

Once the initial evaluation was completed, the samples were split at the sentence level, and the resulting sentence data was used to train a series of NER models, reserving 20% for each of the pilots to serve as a test set.

Figure 6: User interface of the Argilla annotation platform, with a sample from the Neuroscience pilot.

²⁴ docs.argilla.io

For the Neuroscience domain, we used variants of BiomedBERT²⁵ and BioLinkBERT²⁶ as backbones to produce two types of NER models: a model trained *de novo*; and a finetuned version of the AIONER models previously described in D4.1. A third model type was obtained by finetuning a GLiNER model [4]—a powerful generalist framework that enables entity recognition with arbitrary, user-defined natural language label descriptions. For the other three domains, we used RoBERTa²⁷ to train new models, in addition to finetuning a GLiNER model.

After training, and for each pilot, a sample of results from the entity extraction applied to a set of texts that were not present in the original datasets was shared with the domain experts for feedback and model selection. The F1 scores for the models selected for the enrichment—excluding the AIONER models used for the cancer pilot—on the 20% test dataset, obtained using the same scripts as for the previous set of AIONER models, are shown below:

Pilot	Entity	Model	F1
Neuroscience	technique	GLiNER	78.48
	preparation type	GLiNER	66.67
	UBERON parcellation	GLiNER	67.15
	species	GLiNER	65.22
	biological sex	GLiNER	88.00
Energy	energy type	RoBERTa	62.70
	energy storage	RoBERTa	36.36
Transport - Maritime	vessel type	RoBERTa	84.44
Transport - CCAM	vehicle type	RoBERTa - vehicle+VRU	88.89
	VRU type	RoBERTa - vehicle+VRU	80.00
	communication type	RoBERTa - other	66.67
	entity connection type	RoBERTa - other	75.00

²⁵ huggingface.co/microsoft/BiomedNLP-BiomedBERT-base-uncased-abstract-fulltext

²⁶ huggingface.co/michiyasunaga/BioLinkBERT-large

²⁷ huggingface.co/FacebookAI/roberta-large

	sensor type	RoBERTa - other	76.47
	scenario type	RoBERTa - other	50.00
	level of automation	RoBERTa - other	85.71

Table 3: F1 scores of the models selected for domain-specific entity extraction on their corresponding test sets.

We note that, in the case of CCAM, there are 2 separate RoBERTa models. This is due to the fact that initial tests with a single model resulted in confusion and segmentation errors between the *vehicleType* and *VRUType* entities, on the one hand, and the *entityConnectionType*, on the other: e.g., “vehicle-to-pedestrian” could be missed as *entityConnectionType*, while “vehicle” and/or “pedestrian” were extracted as *vehicleType/VRUType*. Additionally, while we acknowledge that the performance of the identification for the *energyStorage* (Energy) and *scenarioType* (CCAM) entities is far from ideal, it was deemed worth it to include both in the extraction in this proof of concept, as the experts found the outputs valuable nonetheless.

NAMED-ENTITY NORMALISATION

Named-entity normalisation (also known as entity linking) is the task of mapping recognised entities to entries in controlled vocabularies or knowledge bases. This step is essential for enabling interoperability and semantic enrichment of the extracted information. The implementation follows a domain-adaptive approach, with different strategies employed based on the characteristics of each domain's vocabulary.

Domain-specific vocabularies

For the normalisation of entities, we employ domain-specific controlled vocabularies tailored to the needs of each pilot:

- **Neuroscience:** openMINDS controlled terms for all entities except for neuroanatomical concepts (*UBERONParcellation*), for which we use the UBERON ontology
- **Cancer:** NCBI Gene for *Gene*, Disease Ontology (DOID) for *Disease*, DrugBank for *Chemical*, NCBI Taxonomy for *Species*, and Brenda Tissue Ontology (BTO) for *CellLine*
- **Energy:** IRENA Energy Taxonomy
- **Transport (Maritime):** AIS vessel type classifications, simplified

- **Transport (CCAM):** ad-hoc CCAM Vocabulary based on SINFONICA and FAME

In addition to these domain-specific sources, Wikidata²⁸ is used as a complementary knowledge base for broader entity coverage.

Linking architecture

The normalisation pipeline employs a two-stage architecture that combines efficient retrieval with accurate validation:

Stage 1 - Candidate retrieval: For each entity mention, candidate concepts are retrieved from the target vocabulary using embedding-based semantic similarity. Entity mentions and vocabulary entries are encoded using multilingual sentence transformers, enabling matching of synonyms and paraphrases beyond exact string matching.

Stage 2 - Validation and ranking: Retrieved candidates are validated using a language model that considers both the entity mention and its surrounding context from the source document. This step enables the system to:

- Disambiguate entities based on context, e.g., distinguishing "solar" as an energy type vs. astronomical reference
- Reject entities that do not belong to the target domain, reducing false positives
- Select the most specific matching concept when multiple candidates are relevant

For domains with large and potentially ambiguous vocabularies—such as the biomedical domain with millions of gene symbols—we employ SQLite-based full-text search indices that provide efficient exact matching with built-in text normalisation—handling variations in spacing, Greek letters, and plural forms. This approach scales to vocabularies with millions of entries while maintaining low memory usage.

An illustration of the combined output of both the NER and NEN modules is shown in Fig. 4.1.3.2.

²⁸ [wikidata.org](https://www.wikidata.org)

Figure 7: Example output showing entities identified by the NER module and linked to controlled vocabularies by the NEN module.

Integration with named-entity recognition

The normalisation module operates on the output of the NER step, processing entities that have been identified but not yet linked to controlled vocabularies. For domains with well-defined, unambiguous terminologies, such as Energy and Neuroscience, a gazetteer-based approach is also employed during the NER step itself, which simultaneously identifies and links entities found in the taxonomy through exact string matching. This

combined approach maximises both precision and recall across different types of entity mentions.

The linked entities, along with their taxonomy identifiers and confidence scores, are integrated into the enriched metadata that is subsequently ingested into the domain-specific SKGs.

PILOT FEEDBACK AND FINAL EXECUTION

The full pipeline has been executed for all pilots on a subset of publication fulltexts from the corresponding graphs gathered with the PDF Fetcher module—see D2.2 (“Final version of the Scientific Lake Service”). In order to showcase the integration potential between different components of the service, these were first processed with the Article Segmentation tool—see below—to extract and link the identified entities at the section level with predefined section titles. In addition to being integrated into the SKGs for querying and exploration, a sample of these extracted mentions was obtained for each pilot for further feedback and future refinement of the NEN module—each mention containing its context, entity type, and linked taxonomy entry in order to assess the quality of the prediction and allowing for corrections.

An overview of the assessment, shown as the share of different types of errors in each output sample, can be found in the Table below:

Pilot	irrelevant entities	segmentation errors	ambiguous entities	missing or incorrect linking
Neuroscience	46.4%	3.3%	2.8%	7.5%
Cancer	2.0%	1.4%	1.4%	10–18.5%*
Energy	18.9%	2.0%	3.0%	17.7%
Transport - Maritime	1.7%	3.4%	28.9%	3.3%
Transport - CCAM	18.7%	5.0%	5.0%	4.5%

Table 4: Pilot feedback on the initial version of the entity recognition and linking for domain-specific concepts. The “missing or incorrect linking” category includes entities that are relevant to the domain and have been linked to a term in the taxonomy when there is a more appropriate term available; and entities that are unlinked when there is an appropriate term in the

taxonomy; but excludes entities that are linked to a term without sufficient information, as these entries are categorised as “ambiguous”. However, it may partially overlap with the “segmentation errors” category.

We note that the share of errors found in each of the samples is overestimated with respect to true random samples due to the fact that the instances selected for the evaluation deliberately include some “problem” entries, such as an overrepresentation of unlinked mentions. For instance:

- ca. 60% of the irrelevant entities in the case of the energy pilot, and ca. 40% in the case of the neuroscience pilot, correspond to unlinked mentions
- An additional 36% of the irrelevant entities in neuroscience correspond to erroneously and greedily linked UBERONParcellation mentions, an entity which the GLiNER model tends to associate with all types of anatomical mentions
- The overwhelming majority of ambiguous mentions in the case of the maritime pilot corresponds to neutral appearances of “ship(s)” or “vessel(s)”

In addition to this, in the case of the cancer pilot, no entries were corrected by the experts in terms of linking. However, we found by inspection that in some cases—in particular for cell lines—there is a synonym in the taxonomy that almost exactly matches the mention and was not linked by the model. The share of unlinked mentions that do not belong to any error category is about 18.5% of the total sample, and we have set it as an upper bound for the share of errors.

After the feedback iteration, some straightforward modifications have been made to the pipeline—e.g., as hinted at above, systematic errors with hardcoded solutions, or strict entity linking scenarios for which potentially relevant but unlinked entities are ignored—and it has been executed on the entirety of the pilot SKGs. Due to volume constraints, especially in the case of the biomedical use cases, this implementation has been limited to the titles and abstracts of the documents in the graphs.

Code repo(s)	github.com/sirisacademic/scilake-enrichments
Model files	huggingface.co/collections/SIRIS-Lab/scilake

Table 5: Links to code repositories and model files pertaining to the domain-specific entity extraction and normalisation pipeline.

4.1.4. Geolocalisation of research outputs

As discussed above, in the case of the Energy pilot there existed a special interest in extracting and integrating geographic information from research outputs; specifically, the focus is georeferencing two key entities: institutions and case study areas. The aim is to enable queries and visualisations that take into account the spatial context within the SKG. This approach facilitates the visualisation of research outputs by institution, identification of research interdependencies, and recognition of key contributors within the field, which could result in more nuanced, location-aware insights, given the spatially contingent nature of energy systems.

GEOGRAPHICAL ENTITY EXTRACTION AND CLASSIFICATION WITH GEORDIE

The Geordie²⁹ tool is used to extract toponyms from titles, abstracts, and full-text publication sections, and semantically classify the role that these geographical mentions play in the text, distinguishing between, e.g., “contextual mention”, “impacted location”, or “object of research”—see below. This tool has been developed outside of the context of SciLake and is described elsewhere [5]. However, a key innovation within the project lies in the identification and georeferencing of “case study” toponyms—a subtype of “object of research” introduced—an underexplored dimension in SKG construction. In this context, a case study refers to an in-depth examination of a specific instance, such as a geographic region, technology, or project, within its real-life energy context, aimed at uncovering detailed insights into processes, outcomes, and contextual challenges.

²⁹ github.com/sirisacademic/geordie

The geotagging tool consists of two distinct elements that work sequentially: first, a NER model that identifies and links geographic entities in text, and second, a classification model that determines the specific role each geographic mention plays within its research context.

1. **Geographic Entity Recognition and Linking**

A multilingual NER model was trained to identify geographic entities across six languages: English, Spanish, Catalan, Italian, French, and German. The model recognises geographic entities in a broad sense, encompassing three main categories: locations (countries, cities, regions, and continents), landmarks (both natural features and human-made structures such as mountains, rivers, and monuments), and geopolitical entities (administrative divisions, territories, and states).

The training process fine-tunes a DistilBERT³⁰ model using multiple existing datasets to ensure robust multilingual coverage. These included the multilingual europarl-ner corpus³¹ covering English, Italian, Spanish, and German; the FewNERD dataset³² for English; and the MultiNERD multilingual dataset³³; in addition to the Catalan Entity Identification and Linking (CEIL) dataset developed³⁴ by the Aina group at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center.

Once geographic entities are identified in text, the system performs disambiguation and linking to OpenStreetMap³⁵ (OSM) as its geographic database. This linking process uses an external geocoding service accessed via HTTP calls, which matches detected mentions to OSM entries based on orthographic similarity. The system applies probability thresholds to filter results and includes post-processing steps to reduce common errors.

This disambiguation step resolves entities with identical names—such as "Springfield", which could refer to locations in Massachusetts, Illinois, or dozens of other U.S. cities—consolidates multiple variants of the same place across different languages and abbreviations—such as "Munich", "München", or "Monaco di Baviera"—and retrieves additional metadata, including geographic coordinates for each identified location. To reduce computational costs from repeated API calls, the system implements an automatic caching mechanism that stores previously retrieved results.

³⁰ huggingface.co/docs/transformers/en/model_doc/distilbert

³¹ github.com/ixa-ehu/ner-evaluation-corpus-europarl

³² huggingface.co/datasets/DFKI-SLT/few-nerd

³³ huggingface.co/datasets/Babelscape/multinerd

³⁴ huggingface.co/datasets/projecte-aina/ceil

³⁵ openstreetmap.org

2. Role Classification of Geographic Mentions

The second component consists of a DistilBERT classifier trained to categorise geographic mentions according to the specific function they serve within academic and research texts. This classification is essential for enabling more granular analysis, defining more meaningful impact indicators, and filtering out noise from irrelevant mentions. Without this classifier, all geographic references would be treated equally, making it difficult to distinguish between, for example, a location that is the primary focus of research versus an institution name that merely indicates where researchers are based.

The classification taxonomy comprises five distinct categories. Category A ("Object of study") identifies when a geographic entity is the primary research focus, including locations of case studies or pilot projects. Category B ("Research location") indicates where the research is conducted, encompassing mentions of research institutions, infrastructure, and fieldwork sites. Category C ("Target audience, beneficiary, or impacted entity") identifies entities, persons, or groups that benefit from or are affected by the research. Category D ("Institutional reference") covers organisations or institutions linked to a geographic entity, excluding research institutions already captured in Category B.

Finally, Category E ("Contextual references and other") includes geographic entities that provide context but are not the main focus, such as comparative examples, historical or cultural context, incidental references, and false positives from the entity recognition model. The classifier represents a prototype in its early training stages, requiring further development before it can be reliably evaluated in production settings.

Figure 8: Geordie pipeline.

Code repo(s)	github.com/sirisacademic/geordie
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Table 6: Link to the code repository of Geordie.

INSTITUTIONAL DISAMBIGUATION WITH AFFILGOOD

The task of automatically identifying organisations in author-provided affiliation strings and linking them to unique identifiers from global, human-curated registries, such as the Research Organization Registry³⁶ (ROR) or Wikidata, is known as institution name disambiguation. These links are crucial for tracking and tackling organisation changes over time—e.g., institutional mergers and splits—in order to accurately attribute research outputs to their contributors, thereby enabling the analysis of research production trends, in addition to fair research assessment. This is challenging due to the fact that affiliation strings that are automatically parsed—from, e.g., PDFs—often include noise, irrelevant information, or typographical errors. Even if this were not the case, the diverse, unstructured ways organisations are referenced by the authors themselves—using different patterns, languages, abbreviations, or

³⁶ ror.org

referring to different institutional levels, such as departments and collaborative institutions—add a significant amount of complexity to this task.

We introduce AffilGood [6] to extract and disambiguate institutional affiliations from article metadata. It provides tools and annotated datasets to improve the accuracy of attributing scientific works to research organisations, especially in multilingual and complex contexts. The framework addresses key challenges in institution name disambiguation through a modular pipeline approach, as shown in the figure below:

Figure 9: AffilGood pipeline.

The modules are:

1. Affiliation span identification

We have annotated a dataset containing ca. 2,000 raw affiliation strings obtained from OpenAlex³⁷ to identify spans containing relevant affiliation data within them. The annotated instances were selected by a stratified random sampling by country, focusing on ensuring diversity in affiliation languages and origins. Additional manually-chosen instances with noisy sequences were deliberately included in the annotated data so we could train our model to filter out non-affiliation strings. Both

³⁷ openalex.org

RoBERTa and XLM-RoBERTa³⁸ models were then fine-tuned to tackle (predominantly) English and multilingual datasets.

2. **Affiliation Entity Recognition**

We defined seven entity types: SUB-ORGANISATION, ORGANISATION, CITY, COUNTRY, ADDRESS, POSTAL-CODE, and REGION. The NER dataset contains over 5,000 raw affiliation strings obtained from OpenAlex, and it includes multilingual samples from all available territories to ensure comprehensive coverage and diversity. As above, we fine-tuned RoBERTa and XLM-RoBERTa models.

Additionally, and considering the fact that affiliation string grammar has its own structure—as opposed to what we would expect from free natural language—we explored whether our affiliation span identification and NER models would benefit from being fine-tuned from models that have been further pre-trained on raw affiliation strings for the masked token prediction task. For this, we adapted the models to 10 million random raw affiliation strings from OpenAlex, achieving competitive performance in the 2 tasks, compared to the base models.

3. **Entity Linking**

The entity linking module connects identified organisations to their corresponding identifiers in external registries such as ROR. It follows a multi-stage approach: candidate retrieval, optional combination of results from multiple retrievers, reranking, and final result selection.

AffilGood provides two retrieval strategies: (i) a Dense Linker, which uses dense vector representations and semantic similarity for matching, offering better handling of name variations, translations, and multilingual contexts through HNSW indices; (ii) a Whoosh Linker, based on full-text search with support for fuzzy matching, acronyms, and location-aware queries. These retrievers can be combined to leverage the strengths of different matching strategies, improving accuracy for complex or ambiguous cases.

To further refine candidate rankings, two reranking mechanisms are available: a Direct Pair Reranker, which compares affiliation strings directly with candidates using text normalisation and variant generation; and an LLM Reranker, which employs large language models for context-aware disambiguation of similar organisations. The framework also supports multiple data sources beyond ROR—including Wikidata integration—and allows users to implement custom data source handlers for domain-specific registries.

³⁸ huggingface.co/docs/transformers/en/model_doc/xlm-roberta

Our approach aims to improve the accuracy of institution name disambiguation in open scholarly databases. While linking to ROR is a widely adopted resource for affiliation normalisation, it presents several limitations, such as limited coverage in certain countries and insufficient representation of non-academic actors—particularly small companies, public administrations, and non-profit organisations—in addition to challenges in distinguishing between different branches of the same organisation, resulting in a lack of granularity and what is known as the “headquarter effect”. To address these gaps, AffilGood provides tools to integrate additional external catalogs and institutional registries, offering broader applicability across use cases. Furthermore, the framework includes geographical metadata enrichment that supports the localisation of organisations at various administrative levels, improving the precision of territorial analysis.

More details of the implementation and evaluation of the component can be found in the repository:

Paper(s)	AffilGood: Building reliable institution name disambiguation tools to improve scientific literature analysis.
Code repo(s)	github.com/sirisacademic/affilgood

Table 7: Link to the paper and code repository of AffilGood.

4.1.5. Extraction of technologies

We employed large language models to construct structured ontologies of technologies across four domains: energy, transport, cancer, neuroscience, and the broader biomedical field. Simple prompting proved insufficient, as it produced a narrow and incomplete set of technologies, so we adopted a recursive prompting strategy with reflection on each extraction step. The process begins by generating a first hierarchical level consisting of subdomains within each domain, representing general technological areas. For every subdomain, we then identify a second level of technology topics, and for each topic we extract a detailed list of specific technologies, including their synonyms and a concise technical description. This iterative approach allows the model to refine and expand its outputs at each stage while maintaining logical consistency across levels.

The resulting ontologies³⁹ are detailed, extensive, and explainable, with clear hierarchical relations from high level subdomains down to individual technologies. Building on these ontologies, we applied natural language processing techniques such as stemming and term normalisation to align the extracted technologies with large-scale textual data for each domain. Occurrences of each technology and its synonyms are grouped under a normalised form, enabling the linking of all documents that contain a given technology entity in any form expressed in the text.

Code repo(s)	github.com/opix-ai/scilake_technology_ontologies
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Table 8: Link to the repository containing the developed ontologies.

4.2. Research object link recommendation

In this section, we introduce two SciLake components (SHINER and SciNeM) designed to recommend links between Knowledge Graph (KG) nodes, particularly research objects. These recommended links may be missing from the respective KGs and can be used to enrich them and further improve their coverage. In the next sections, first, we provide background on the problem of research object link recommendation and explain how it can help in enhancing research reproducibility. Then, we provide the technical details related to each of the aforementioned components.

4.2.1. Background

Components that are able to identify links between research objects (such as datasets, publications, and software) and research entities (such as authors, institutions, and funding sources), which are missing from existing SKGs, are invaluable for enhancing the reproducibility of scientific research. By pinpointing these missing connections, the component ensures that all relevant resources and contributors are comprehensively documented and interconnected. This comprehensive mapping makes it possible for researchers to trace the provenance and context of each research output, providing a clear and detailed account of how data was collected, analysed, and interpreted. As a result, other researchers can more accurately replicate the study's methodology and validate its findings, which is a cornerstone of scientific reproducibility.

³⁹ github.com/opix-ai/scilake_technology_ontologies

Moreover, identifying missing links can reveal previously overlooked relationships and dependencies that are critical for understanding the full scope of a research project. For example, linking datasets to their originating experiments or software tools to their specific applications can highlight the intricate workflows involved in scientific research. This transparency not only aids in reproducibility but also fosters collaboration and knowledge sharing. Researchers can build upon existing work with greater confidence, knowing that they have a complete picture of the tools, data, and methodologies involved. Additionally, funding bodies and institutions can use these insights to ensure compliance with open science mandates and to promote practices that enhance the credibility and impact of their supported research.

Ultimately, components that provide missing links between research objects and entities, can act in a complementary fashion with those that reveal similar links by identifying mentions in scientific texts (like those presented in the previous section). These two categories of tools combined have the potential to significantly increase the coverage of SKGs regarding the respective types of links.

4.2.2. sHINER: the Graph Generating Dependency approach

sHINER⁴⁰ is a tool that can be used to recommend missing links among graph entities based on a predefined set of Graph Generating Dependencies (GGDs) [7]. GGDs represent a novel class of dependencies for property graphs, extending the concept of tuple-generating dependencies to graph data. GGDs express constraints between two potentially different graph patterns, enforcing relationships based on both data properties and graph topology. This class of dependencies addresses the need for advanced data management techniques in graph-structured data, facilitating tasks such as data integration, data quality assurance, and query optimisation.

Since D4.1, several advances have been made in GGD research and tooling. The GGDMiner framework [7b], published at CIKM 2024, enables automatic discovery of GGDs from graph data using a novel Answer Graph technique, a factorised representation that achieves orders-of-magnitude improvements in execution time and memory efficiency. A comprehensive treatment of GGD reasoning (satisfiability, implication, validation) was published in Information Sciences [7c], establishing complexity bounds and Chase-based algorithms for GGD enforcement. Further, the sHINER system has been improved with a REST API mode for integration with the ProGGD graph profiling interface. Two validation algorithms

⁴⁰ github.com/avantlab/gcore-spark-ggd

have been implemented using "left anti-join" and "left outer-join" approaches, with the anti-join variant showing better scalability on LDBC benchmark datasets.

In the context of SciLake, we used sHINER to link entities in Scientific KGs (SKGs). An indicative example of this was a GGD used for link recommendation for the OpenAIRE Graph to suggest links between results and projects, in case that the result has author(s) from an organisation that participates in the respective project. Figure 4.2.2.1 [10] illustrates the respective GGD: its main goal is to connect each project to all results the organisation has previously worked on. By linking the project to the results we can easily visualise how different projects relate to the same result and consequently use these new links to make queries automatically.

Figure 10: Illustration of the GGD used to suggest links between projects and results in the OpenAIRE Graph based on the organisations involved in the results.

sHINER has also been applied for entity resolution between heterogeneous Knowledge Graphs. In the Cancer pilot, GGDs were used to identify matching entities between the Clinical Knowledge Graph and the OpenAIRE Graph by encoding similarity conditions on DOI attributes along with topological constraints. When a GGD detects that a Publication from the Clinical Knowledge Graph and a Result from the OpenAIRE Graph have nearly identical DOIs, sHINER generates a "sameAs" edge linking them. This approach provides explainable entity resolution rules that combine attribute similarity with graph structure.

Paper(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Discovering Graph Generating Dependencies for Property Graph Profiling • Reasoning on property graphs with graph generating dependencies • On Graph Generating Dependencies and their Applications in Data Profiling • ProGGD-Data Profiling on Knowledge Graphs using Graph Generating Dependencies • Graph Profiling with Graph Generating Dependencies
Code repo(s)	github.com/avantlab/gcore-spark-ggd

Table 9: Links to SHINER publications and code repository.

4.2.3. SciNeM: the metapath approach

SciNeM⁴¹ [8], a powerful Knowledge Graph (KG) analysis engine, focuses on a particular type of KG analysis, called “metapath-based analysis”. This type of analysis is capable of exploiting the structure of the graph to extract latent knowledge (e.g., missing links) that is encoded inside it. To better understand the respective concept, we need to provide a quick introduction on the main terms involved.

KGs offer an intuitive and generic model to encapsulate complex semantic information via different types of nodes and edges, which both have internal structure including a set of properties. The next figure illustrates an example graph with its schema (that can be explicitly or implicitly defined). It consists of nodes representing papers (P), authors (A), venues (V), and topics (T) and (bidirectional) edges of three types: authors – papers (AP / PA), papers – topics (PT / TP), and papers – venues (PV / VP).

⁴¹ <https://github.com/athenarc/SciNeM-workflows> & <https://github.com/athenarc/SciNeM>

Figure 11: A KG example.

Indirect relationships between entities are implicitly encoded by paths in the graph. All paths that correspond to the same sequence of node and edge types (i.e., the same “metapath” [9]) encode latent relationships of the same interpretation between the starting and ending nodes. In the above example, the metapath $\langle APTPA \rangle$ relates authors that have published papers on the same topic (e.g., both “J. Doe” and “H. Jekyll” have papers about “DL”). Notice that each metapath corresponds to a path on the schema of the graph. Metapaths are instrumental for KG analysis: the metapath-based connectivity can be used to define node similarity measures or to rank nodes based on their centrality in a metapath-defined graph/network. In our example, using $\langle TPT \rangle$ to perform a similarity join could reveal that topics “ML” and “DL” are very related since they are involved in two common papers. To further elaborate the analysis, it is often useful to apply property-based constraints to metapaths (e.g., to consider only metapath instances involving papers published later than “2020”). It should be noted that the first step in any metapath-based analysis is to generate a transformed graph that contains edges between all pairs of nodes connected with one or more paths of a specified type.

Based on the previous discussion, it is now easier to understand the various components of the SciNeM tool. The following figure presents the high-level architecture of SciNeM.

Figure 12: Overview of the SciNeM architecture.

SciNeM is a distributed analysis tool that can be deployed on an Apache Spark⁴² computational cluster. Its storage layer, which stores all KG data, utilises a Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS) hosted on the storage media of the underlying computational cluster. Each KG comprises a set of files, including:

- a **schema file** (compatible with Cytoscape's⁴³ Elements JSON format) that describes the node types of the KG and the types of relationships among them,
- **node files** in TSV format containing data attributes for the nodes of each type, and
- **relationship files** that define the network edges.

User-created KGs, which are compatible with the previous format, can be uploaded to SciNeM's distributed storage layer via its web-based user interface (UI).

The core of the SciNeM tool is its graph transformation component. This component implements the common preprocessing step that converts the initial heterogeneous graph into a transformed version that contains edges between all pairs of nodes connected with one or more paths of a specified type. The type of paths is given by the user and it essentially captures latent relationships with particular semantics. The transformed graph is later used to apply a desired type of analysis on top. In the context of the SciLake project, our interest was on missing links recommendations. We started working on some relationship types of the OpenAIRE Graph that were deemed interesting, where there was space for improvements in the coverage. For instance, we explored providing recommendations for linking publications to projects or communities by analysing the similarity between new publications and those

⁴² spark.apache.org

⁴³ cytoscape.org

already associated with the target project or community. To this end, we used metapath-based similarities with interesting semantics, following a similar approach like the one we have used in the past for another work [10].

It is worth mentioning that, since the calculation of the transformed graph is a computationally intensive task, special care was taken for the efficient implementation of this component. In the original version, the core of the transformation is calculated using matrix multiplication between the adjacency matrices defined by the relations of the given metapath. Specifically, our approach is based on the work in [11] but extends it by utilising sparse matrix representations. Since the order of multiplications significantly affects the performance of the whole processing, we adopt a dynamic programming approach that estimates the optimal ordering taking into consideration the computational cost of sparse matrix multiplications introduced in [12]. This modification offers significant speedups, compared to the baseline, in many cases. In addition, since the implementation of this component utilises Apache Spark, it takes advantage of parallel and distributed computing.

In the context of the project, we have also investigated a different approach, called Atrapos [13], which efficiently detects, in real time, frequent metapath overlaps within a sequence of queries. To do so, it uses: (i) sparse matrix representations, which leverage the fact that matrices involved in metapath computations are largely sparse, especially for constrained metapaths; and (ii) a tailored data structure with a customised caching policy to materialise reoccurring intermediate results. Our experimental evaluation demonstrated that Atrapos outperforms traditional, single-query approaches in the evaluation of metapath query workloads, while it is considerably faster than baseline approaches. The detailed methodology and experiments can be found in the original publication.

Paper(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• SciNeM: A Scalable Data Science Tool for Heterogeneous Network Mining• Atrapos: Real-time Evaluation of Metapath Query Workloads.
Code repo(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• https://github.com/athenarc/SciNeM-workflows• https://github.com/athenarc/SciNeM• https://github.com/schatzopoulos/ATRAPOS

Table 10: Links to SciNeM and Atrapos publications and code repositories.

4.3. Article segmentation for multilingual articles

In this section, we introduce two SciLake components (Article Segmentation and Automatic Translation) designed to recognise the structure of scientific documents and to translate content automatically.

4.3.1. Article Segmentation

The objective of this tool is the recognition of the structure of scientific documents, especially identifying its constituent parts (sections and titles), coupled with the classification of these parts into predefined section types—e.g., the conclusions in a scientific paper could be named in many ways, such as ‘Conclusions’, ‘Conclusions and Future Work’, ‘Discussion’, etc.

This functionality is depicted in Figure 4.3.1.1 [13].

Figure 13: Article Segmentation for scientific articles.

SCIENTIFIC ARTICLE STRUCTURE DETECTION (SEGMENTATION)

As described in D4.1, the first step in the pipeline leverages GROBID⁴⁴ to process PDF documents and identify their structural components, such as headings, texts, tables, etc., offering three output formats:

- XML format using TEI schema.
- JSON format using TEI schema.
- RDF format mapped from TEI.

In Table 4.3.1.1 [11] an XML example output of Grobid is shown.

The tool is provided as a docker container so that it can be utilised completely independently, without any special configuration needed.

⁴⁴ github.com/kermitt2/grobid

```

<teiHeader xml:lang="en">
  <fileDesc>
    <titleStmt><title level="a" type="main">Organization of Posterior Parietal-Frontal
Connections in the Rat</title></titleStmt>
    <publicationStmt>
    <availability status="unknown"><licence/></availability>
    <date type="published" when="2019-08-21">21 August 2019</date>
    </publicationStmt>
    <sourceDesc><biblStruct><author><persName><forename
type="first">Gilad</forename><surname>Silberberg</surname></persName></author>
</biblStruct></sourceDesc></fileDesc>
    <profileDesc>
    <abstract><div xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"><p>Recent investigations of the rat
posterior parietal cortex (PPC) suggest that this region plays a central role in action control
together with the frontal cortical areas. [...] </p></div></abstract>
    </profileDesc>
  </teiHeader>
<text xml:lang="en"> <body> [...]
```

Table 11: XML Example of the output of Grobid.

SCIENTIFIC ARTICLE SECTION CLASSIFICATION

During the second half of the project, we have redefined the architecture of this component (shown in Figure 4.3.1.2 [14]).

Figure 14: Scientific Article Section Classification.

We have trained five domain specific hierarchical text classifiers to automatically assign each part of the text to a predefined section class, based on a self-defined and annotated dataset, namely SASC dataset. This dataset has been annotated using a self-defined 2-level taxonomy for a hierarchical section classification approach. The 2-level taxonomy is presented in Table 4.3.1.2 [12].

ID	L=1 Class Label	L=2 Class Label	Description
1	Introduction	background, problem statement, objectives, contributions, outline	Context, problem statement, research gap, and paper goals. Corresponds to I in IMRaD.
2	Related Work	literature review, theoretical framework, gaps identified	Review of prior literature and state-of-the-art methods.
3	Method	study design, participants, data collection, procedures, statistical analysis, ethical considerations, materials and instruments, data preprocessing, evaluation, case study	Description of the system, materials, models, or procedures used. Corresponds to M in IMRaD.
4	Experiment	descriptive statistics, main findings, secondary findings, tables figures, statistical tests, evaluation	Details on experimental setup, data, metrics, and results. Closely tied to R in IMRaD.
5	Discussion	interpretation, comparison literature, implications, limitations, strengths, future work	Interpretation, implications, limitations, and future work. Corresponds to D in IMRaD.
6	Conclusion	summary, key findings, contributions, final remarks, future directions recommendations	Final summary of findings and concluding remarks.
7	Other	-	Unclassified sections.
8	Appendix/Misc.	supplementary data, additional analyses, technical details, code and materials, ethics and consent, compliance statement	Supplementary or procedural material directly related to the study: extended analyses, code, data, technical documentation, and ethical or compliance statements to the research process.
9	Metadata	acknowledgments, authorship, funding, license, data code materials availability, publisher note	Sections providing administrative or provenance information about the publication itself: author roles, funding sources, legal licenses, and data-sharing declarations. Not part of the scientific argument but essential for transparency and reproducibility.

Table 12: 2-level taxonomy defined for the SASC dataset (shows labels from levels 1 and 2).

Using this dataset, we have trained and evaluated the first model (shown in Table 4.3.1.3). The results are promising, although we found out that the model is overfitting.

Model	Epoch 1			Epoch 5		
	loss	l1_acc	l2_acc	loss	l1_acc	l2_acc
Training	0.5731	0.6362	0.9407	0.1204	0.9389	0.9848
Validation	0.4634	0.7059	0.9580	0.5134	0.7619	0.9616

Table 13: Evaluation Results of Hierarchical Text Classification.

Looking at the results, it is clear that the model is overfitting. By epoch 5, the model fits the training data very well, but this does not translate into much better performance on validation data. Epoch 1 already captures most of what the model can generalise; training longer mainly helps the model memorise the training set. In other words, later epochs improve training accuracy more than real-world performance. Fine-tuning increases the model's maximum achievable accuracy, but also makes it easier to overfit. Without fine-tuning, the model is more stable, but its performance is restricted. Level 1 benefits more from fine-tuning, while Level 2 is mostly unaffected.

USEFUL RESOURCES

The next table summarises the most important resources (publications, code repositories, etc) related to the DSR component.

Code repo(s)	https://gitlab.com/dfki-scilake/dsr
Docker URL	registry.gitlab.com/dfki-scilake/dsr:d41

Table 14: Links to code repositories and documentation of the DSR component.

4.3.2. Automatic translation

For the automatic translation service, we started by developing a suite of Neural Machine Translation (NMT) models targeting the language pairs of Spanish-English, French-English, and Portuguese-English. Using meticulously curated corpora, including general and domain-specific scientific content in order to address the needs of the project pilots, we fine-tuned pre-trained NMT models from OPUS-MT [14] for each language pair, which are available on the Hugging Face platform:

- **French-English:** huggingface.co/ilsp/opus-mt-big-fr-en_ct2_ft-SciLake
- **Portuguese-English:** huggingface.co/ilsp/opus-mt-pt-en_ct2_ft-SciLake
- **Spanish-English:** huggingface.co/ilsp/opus-mt-big-es-en_ct2_ft-SciLake

The details of the training and evaluation of the models are described in D4.1.

During the second half of the project, our approach to automatic translation evolved significantly based on pilot evaluations. Our findings revealed that while traditional NMT models, like the ones which we produced based on OPUS-MT, are efficient, they often struggle with the syntactic complexity and specialised discourse of scientific writing.

Furthermore, the evolving needs of the pilots introduced a requirement for German translation, a language not originally foreseen and for which we lacked specialised NMT models for the science domain. This gap, combined with the rapid advancement of Large Language Models (LLMs) during the project's timeline offered a superior alternative for handling complex, domain-specific tasks. Consequently, by the time the pilots required machine translation services, we transitioned from our initial NMT models to state-of-the-art open-source LLMs. Specifically we selected Cohere's Aya Expanse (8B & 32B) and Google's Gemma3-27b-it, all deployed on our team's hardware.

Utilizing Gemma3-27b-it, we successfully executed a series of diverse and large-scale translation tasks tailored to the specific needs of the project pilots:

- **Energy Pilot Support & Keyword Filtering:** We analyzed the SciPar dataset for the Energy pilot, refining an initial keyword list to a strict 75-keyword set to filter out false positives. This process identified over 2,000 highly relevant parallel abstracts for the pilot. Additionally, to support legal documentation integration, we translated 5,234 German legal documents from the Swiss FedLex dataset into English.
- **OpenAIRE Community Gateway Translation:** Leveraging our fine-tuned OPUS-MT models, we translated non-English abstracts and titles for specific OpenAIRE communities. Following data preprocessing and language identification, we translated 1,384 documents for the transport domain, 12,822 for neuroscience, and 62 for cancer research from French, Portuguese, and Spanish into English.
- **Transport-CCAM Legal Documentation:** For the Transport pilot, we translated a curated selection of legal documents from French, Spanish, Portuguese, and German into English. This task required extracting text from PDFs (utilizing the Jina AI Reader API), chunking, translating with Gemma3, and applying a secondary post-editing step with the LLM to correct extraction artifacts and inconsistencies.
- **Large-Scale OpenAIRE Graph Integration:** In a major effort to enhance the accessibility of the OpenAIRE Graph, we translated hundreds of thousands of titles and abstracts. Collaborating with OPIX for language identification (filtering for 100% confidence scores), we utilised the Gemma3-27b-it model to translate 4,730 Portuguese, 46,280 French, and 619,826 Spanish documents into English. Additionally, within a specific Maritime dataset, we translated another 195 documents across the three languages.

4.4. SciNoBo CA tool: Citation-context assisted replication assessment

This section describes the final version of the SciNoBo Citation-context Assisted (CA) Replication Assessment tool, building upon the initial implementation presented in D4.1 (“Initial version of the smart reproducibility assistance service”). Since the delivery of the initial version, the component has been extended and refined, with improvements in the underlying ontology, the training data, and the modelling approaches used for citance analysis. These improvements aim to increase robustness, and domain coverage (Energy, Neuroscience, Cancer and Transport).

The SciNoBo Citation-context Assisted (CA) Replication Assessment tool analyses citation mentions (citances) in scientific publications in order to provide a fine-grained characterisation of how prior work is referenced, reused, extended, or challenged.

By analysing the textual context in which citations occur, the tool supports a more nuanced assessment of scientific reuse, validation, and rebuttal, which are key aspects for evaluating reproducibility and replicability beyond citation counts.

For each citance, the tool jointly analyses three dimensions:

- **Citation Intent**, capturing the purpose of the citation from the perspective of the citing author.
- **Citation Polarity**, capturing the stance expressed towards the cited work.
- **Citation Semantics**, capturing the specific aspect of the cited work that is being referenced.

This multidimensional representation enables the identification of citations that signal reuse of methods or artefacts, extension of prior approaches, comparison with related work, or refutation of claims.

DRAFT

Figure 15: Example citances and their corresponding classifications across the Semantics, Intent, and Polarity categories, based on the ontology defined in this work. Each citance mark in the same sentence can have similar or different categories.

Methodology

Citances are provided from publication full texts, together with their surrounding paragraph-level context. Each citance is treated as a distinct analytical unit and is explicitly associated with a specific citation marker to avoid ambiguity in sentences containing multiple references. The extracted citances are then analysed using a unified ontology and a set of trained language models that jointly classify Intent, Polarity, and Semantics.

Citance Classification Ontology

The SciNoBo CA tool relies on a structured ontology that organises citance analysis along three orthogonal dimensions.

Intent captures the author's purpose for citing a work and includes the following categories:

- *Generic*: the citation provides background or general context.
- *Reuse*: elements of the cited work are directly reused.
- *Comparison*: the cited work is explicitly compared with the current contribution.
- *Extension*: the cited work is extended or built upon.

Polarity captures the stance of the citing author:

- *Supporting*: the cited work is endorsed or positively acknowledged.
- *Neutral*: the citation is descriptive and does not express an explicit stance.
- *Refuting*: the cited work is questioned or contradicted.

Semantics captures the referenced aspect of the cited work:

- *Claim*: reference to hypotheses, theories, or conceptual statements.
- *Results*: reference to empirical findings or outcomes.
- *Methodology*: reference to experimental or analytical procedures.
- *Artifact*: reference to concrete research artefacts such as datasets, software, models, or tools.

Each citance is assigned exactly one label per dimension, allowing the three dimensions to be analysed independently or jointly.

Dataset Construction and Annotation

To support training and evaluation, a multidisciplinary dataset of annotated citances was constructed. Citances were extracted from publications spanning Engineering and Technology (contains Energy), Health Sciences and Bioinformatics (contains Neuroscience and Cancer), and Social Sciences and Humanities (contains logistics & transportation), covering a broad range of subfields. Sampling was performed to ensure diversity across publication years and citation counts.

Each citance was manually annotated according to the three ontology dimensions. To address sparsity in less frequent category combinations, a limited amount of synthetic data was generated and manually validated. The final dataset consists of 1,165 annotated citances, covering the majority of possible combinations of Intent, Polarity, and Semantics.

Inter-annotator agreement analysis shows strong reliability for Intent and Polarity and moderate agreement for Semantics, reflecting the higher complexity of identifying the referenced aspect of a cited work.

Intent	Count	Percentage	Semantics	Count	Percentage	Polarity	Count	Percentage	Synthetic	Count	Percentage
Comparison	225	19.31	Artifact	346	29.70	Neutral	826	70.90	Non-Synthetic	1,040	89.27
Extension	100	8.58	Claim	259	22.23	Refuting	156	13.39	Synthetic	125	10.73
Generic	603	51.76	Methodology	361	30.99	Supporting	183	15.71			
Reuse	237	20.35	Results	199	17.08						
Total	1,165	100	Total	1,165	100	Total	1,165	100	Total	1,165	100

Table 15: Descriptive statistics of the dataset for the categories: Intent, Semantics, Polarity, and Synthetic distribution. Numbers under percentage columns are in %.

Model Architectures and Training

To implement citation-context assisted replication assessment and based on the previous deliverable (D4.1) several language model architectures were explored. The objective was to assess different modelling paradigms for classifying citances according to Semantics, Intent, and Polarity, while ensuring feasibility within the computational resources of the SciLake project.

Across all approaches, and based on previous work [16] a common preprocessing strategy was applied. Citation markers were normalised to a dedicated placeholder token (<CIT>) during both training and inference, reducing bias from author names or venues and focusing model attention on citation context. For encoder-based architectures, citation markers were replaced with the [MASK] token.

We explored and experimented with the following architectures:

Decoder-only language model: LLaMA 3.1

A decoder-only large language model based on LLaMA 3.1 was fine-tuned for the citance classification task. A quantised version of the model was used to reduce memory requirements and improve training efficiency. Fine-tuning was performed using Quantized Low-Rank Adaptation (QLoRA), restricting parameter updates to low-rank adapters while keeping the base model weights frozen.

Training and inference were implemented using the Unsloth framework⁴⁵, which provides optimised pipelines for parameter-efficient fine-tuning. The model was trained to generate structured outputs encoding Semantics, Intent, and Polarity from the citance context, enabling prediction of the three dimensions in a single inference step.

⁴⁵ <https://github.com/unslothai/unsloth>

Encoder-decoder model: Flan-T5

An encoder-decoder architecture based on Flan-T5 was also fine-tuned. In this setup, citance analysis is framed as an instruction-based sequence-to-sequence task. Training data are formatted as input-output pairs, where the input consists of a short instructional prompt followed by the citance sentence, and the output encodes the labels for Semantics, Intent, and Polarity in a fixed order. This formulation leverages the instruction-following capabilities of the model and produces outputs that can be directly parsed into structured annotations.

Encoder-based multitask classifier: SciBERT

A third approach is based on a custom multitask classification architecture built on top of SciBERT, a model pretrained on large-scale scientific text. In this architecture, the contextual embedding corresponding to the [MASK] token is extracted and passed through a shared multilayer perceptron (MLP) for feature compression.

From this shared representation, three task-specific MLP heads are instantiated to predict Semantics, Intent, and Polarity respectively. ReLU activations are used to introduce non-linearity. The model is trained in a multitask setting using a combined loss function that aggregates the losses of the three tasks. Model selection is performed by maximising the aggregated F1 score across all dimensions.

Figure 16: Architecture of Custom SciBERT Multi-Task classifier.

Results and integration with SciLake

Model	Semantic			Intent			Polarity		
	macro F1	weighted F1	accuracy	macro F1	weighted F1	accuracy	macro F1	weighted F1	accuracy
Llama 3.1-FT	80.05	81.00	81.15	71.36	75.78	76.23	59.87	71.87	76.64
SciBERT MT Class	77.39	78.25	78.28	79.41	81.42	81.97	58.59	69.04	75.41
Flan T5 Base FT	66.28	64.48	64.75	67.81	74.85	74.18	58.97	69.95	74.18
Llama 3.1 Base	62.01	62.40	62.76	66.56	70.08	69.87	54.16	65.27	63.59
GPT-4o mini	58.34	58.94	59.43	64.55	66.73	67.21	58.71	62.58	60.65

Table 16: F1 scores (macro and weighted) and accuracy for each language model across semantic, intent, and polarity tasks on the dataset. Numbers are in % and calculated on the test set. The models of Llama 3.1 Base and GPT-4o mini were used in a few-shot examples setting as baselines.

Overall, the results demonstrate the clear benefit of fine-tuning on the citance dataset and ontology. Fine-tuned models consistently outperform their non-adapted counterparts across all three dimensions, confirming that performance gains are driven by effective adaptation to the specific characteristics of citance analysis rather than general language understanding alone. In particular, substantial improvements were observed when comparing fine-tuned models to their base versions, especially for the Semantics and Intent dimensions.

Model performance varies slightly across dimensions. For Semantic classification, the fine-tuned LLaMA-based model achieved the strongest overall results, with similar macro and weighted F1 scores, indicating stable performance across both frequent and less frequent classes. The SciBERT-based multitask model followed closely, demonstrating competitive performance while maintaining lower inference complexity. For Intent classification, the SciBERT multitask model achieved the highest overall scores, reflecting its strong ability to capture rhetorical and functional patterns in scientific text, likely supported by its domain-specific pretraining. For Polarity classification, performance differences across models were smaller, with both SciBERT and LLaMA-based models achieving comparable results, suggesting that polarity cues are more uniformly captured across architectures.

Taking into account both classification performance and operational considerations, the SciBERT-based multitask model was selected for integration into the SciLake pipelines. This choice reflects a trade-off between predictive performance and inference speed, which is critical for large-scale processing of scientific corpora. The outputs currently integrated into the Scientific Knowledge Graphs are generated using this model. A representative sample of these results has been provided to the SciLake pilots for qualitative evaluation and feedback.

Code repo(s)	https://github.com/iNoBo/scinobo-citance-analysis
Docker hub	https://hub.docker.com/repository/docker/intelligencenoborders/scinobo-citance-analysis/general
HF Space (Demo)	https://huggingface.co/spaces/iNoBo/scinobo-citance-analysis

Table 17: Links to resources corresponding to the citance analysis component.

5. Reproducibility Assistant Portals

SciLake partners have implemented a reproducibility assistant portal for each pilot, which leverages the technologies described in the previous sections, to offer an array of reproducibility-related functionalities to the respective research communities, and to demonstrate their power in practice. Similarly to the SciLake Knowledge Discovery Portal (see Section 4.4 of D3.2), these portals were built upon the BIP! Spaces⁴⁶ service, which acted as the backbone for hosting an array of reproducibility features within a more complete user interface. A screenshot of one of the reproducibility assistant portals is depicted in Figure 4.5.1 [17].

Figure 17: Search result item of the reproducibility assistant portals.

Each portal offers advanced keyword-based search capabilities for scientific publications, incorporating a set of reproducibility-related badges in the list of search results. There are two main types of badges, which are offered by the portals:

⁴⁶ BIP! Spaces: <https://bip.imsi.athenarc.gr/spaces>

- *Reproducibility readiness badges.* These badges appear in a search result in case key research artefacts relevant to the reproducibility or replicability of the work are known to be available. The focus is on datasets and software tools used in the experiments of the work. A distinct badge has been designed for each type of artefact and it is displayed when the metadata indicates that the respective artefact is available. The badges are shown in the top row of the search result (see Figure 4.5.1 [17]).
- *Replication degree indicators.* A set of indicators that estimate the extent to which a study has already been tested and confirmed by subsequent studies. The values of these indicators are displayed as a special type of result annotations, at the bottom of each search result (see Figure 4.5.1 [17]). Three such indicators have been included in the portals:
 - Positive mentions count: The total number of positive (supporting) citations to the study by subsequent studies. Indicating a generic “reputation” that the work has in subsequent literature.
 - Repro Confidence index (RCI): An index that considers the number of positive (supporting), neutral, and negative (refuting) citations a work has received. Each type of citation is weighted to reflect its influence on the perceived reproducibility of the artefact:
$$RCI = (pos_citations + 0.5 * neu_citations - neg_citations) / total_citations$$
A higher RCI indicates that the artefact is generally viewed as reproducible, based on the feedback it has received.
 - Focused RCI: A variant of RCI that considers only citations that had a “comparison” intent. The calculation formula remains the same.

The calculation of the reproducibility readiness badges is possible leveraging both the outputs of the SciNoBo RAA tool (Section 4.1.2) and existing metadata that can be collected by the OpenAIRE Graph (based on the collected relationships between the respective types of research products). For replication degree indicators, the calculation was performed using the outputs of the SciNoBo CA tool (Section 4.4), mainly the classifications for citation polarity and intent.

At this point, it is worth mentioning that the badges and indicators demonstrated in the SciLake reproducibility assistant portals were selected after internal consultation between the project partners and are just an indicative set that aims to demonstrate the value of the various SciLake components. In general, there is a wide variety of reproducibility-related badges and indicators that can be calculated using the SciLake components described in the previous sections of this report.

The reproducibility assistant portals can be used by the researchers in various ways. First, researchers can leverage the keyword-based search functionalities to search for publications

related to a subject of interest. The provided badges and indicators can help them prioritise their reading by highlighting works that are easier to be reproduced or those that are more trustworthy due to confirmation by multiple subsequent studies. Apart from that, researchers can use the same functionality to locate their own works and identify those that are not reproducibility-ready, allowing them to address the issue by making the data or software publicly available.

6. Conclusions

We have presented the final version of the Smart Reproducibility Assistance Service, which incorporates methodologies such as text mining, link prediction, and citation context analysis to enhance the Scientific Knowledge Graphs within the Scientific Lake. Leveraging the contents of the underlying SKGs, the components of the service come together to guide researchers in the discovery of credible research outputs in the respective SKGs, based on an assessment of their reproducibility and replicability. This development aims to provide researchers with tools to better understand and pursue reproducibility in scientific findings.

Building upon the work performed towards the initial version of the service, the developments during the second half of the project have focused on expanding the scope and capabilities of the components involved, improving accuracy, implementing new models, and showcasing their interoperability. All of this has been carried out in close cooperation with pilot representatives in order to provide a tailored experience that meets their domain-specific needs, while allowing flexibility for adaptation to other research communities.

7. References

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